

**CHOICE OF A CHILD-REFUGEE AS A TRAUMATIC
NARRATING VOICE IN MARIE-THÉRÈSE TOYI'S
*WEEP NOT, REFUGEE***

By

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Abstract:

Marie-Thérèse Toyi's *Weep Not, Refugee*, a Burundian, East African prose, is a lucid testimonial literature on suffering, violence and pain (all of which are experiences which may culminate in, or evoke the trauma import) in many areas of the human actors that populate the world of the novel, actors who lived with the resultant traumas, thereafter. This study takes account of linguistic descriptions, stylistic analysis and literary interpretations as these theories permit, in a wide range, the analysis of a contemporary style of writing that incorporates what I may refer to as *faction*, that is, a literary espousal of facts and fiction. This framework is deemed proper for the analysis because "stylistics mediates between the disciplines of linguistics and literary criticism, applying the problems in literary analysis, and the methods and insights of literary criticism to the analysis of language" (Cureton, 1992:81). The study, therefore, seeks to unveil the stylistic choice, characteristics and formal techniques employed by Marie- Thérèse Toyi in her novel, *Weep Not, Refugee*, to establish her child refugee cum narrator's individual subjectivity while also examining the moments when the author speaks through her narrator, using the voice of a child protagonist as a tool to express traumatic historical events and experiences. The study also highlights how the child-refugee is represented textually and linguistically and how he presents himself to the implied addressee of his first-person narration.

Key Words: Linguistic descriptions, Trauma, Stylistic analysis, Literary interpretation, and *Weep Not, Refugee*

Introduction:

Post-independence literatures of many francophone African countries, especially in East Africa, to a large extent, narrate stories of civil war, ethnic conflicts, religious tensions, displacement, violence and the after effects on the populace. Most literary writings from authors like Sony Labou Tansi, Emmanuel Dongala, Boubacar Boris Diop, Esther Mujawayo, among others make reference to gruesome killings, murder and dismemberment in their creative works and these represent accounts of violence in various francophone African countries. Such works also showcase the after-effects and consequences of such occurrences. Burundi is a francophone, East African nation, and Marie-Thérèse Toyi's novel, *Weep Not, Refugee*, published in 2014, ably reflects and captures such hideous occurrences mentioned above and their after-effects on the people of Burundi.

As an experience, the manifestation of trauma is universal. Its global assertiveness is made patent consequent upon a felt shock or hysteria following grave negative developments. These developments are often borne out of cases of injustice, haplessness, gruesome murders, horror, lack, deprivations and the likes. The literary expression of trauma in African literature is not directly made manifest. However, 'trauma reading' can be inferred or deciphered from the way situations are constructed or presented in literary works. Trauma is more of a medical case; it can become a social one in acute traumatic cases especially in situations whereby the person so traumatized loses his mental or psychological equilibrium thus ending up as a societal wreck. It becomes clear from the above that the response which trauma elicits or evokes depends, first on the ability of the individual to contain or mitigate trauma, thus suppressing its explosion, and secondly, on the degree or magnitude of the trauma-provoking situation. My argument here is that suffering in itself is not traumatic; neither is pain, rape, deprivations, horror, gruesome murder and so forth. It is the effect which these negative and terrible manifestations produce on the individual or a group that determines or provokes the traumatic experience. Therefore, one can make a case for individual or group traumas. I have also argued earlier that one can generate trauma-reading in texts based on the situations so described by the author since trauma, itself, finds existence and credence not in the expressed situation but in one's reaction to it. To this end, therefore, the compartmentalization of trauma may pigeon-hole trauma as a psycho-emotional and mental

phenomenon. It takes place in the psyche of the individual and it is what either urges him on or ruins him.

As a nation, Burundi boasts of a good topography comprising of excellent landscapes, beautiful hills and great lakes. Burundi is also a country that has had her fair share of internecine wars consequent upon ethnic jingoism, tribal differences and cultural hegemony. When the story started in *Weep Not, Refugee*, the geo-linguistic setting of the novel was at Mabanu Camp in Wirodi but the story later moved to Burundi. The novel gives an insight into ethnic crisis between the Hutus and the Tutsis, two cardinal ethnic groups in Burundi, during the civil war. The novel immensely recounts the disillusionment, deprivations, agonies, marginalization, injustice, hunger, displacement, rape, human disappearances and other traumatic experiences of the refugees in the camp. Sadly, therefore, a camp that is intended as a safe haven for the refugees ends up becoming their worst nightmare because of their harrowing experiences.

In the novel, the story commences with the sounding of drums of war, announcing "another war, the nth war" (sic) (3). The announcement comes in a horror-filled and traumatic language choice that projects the gravity of an imminent violence in the Great Lakes Region. The text recounts the tragic and traumatic stories of Kigeme, an Hutu orphan girl, who witnessed how an officer of the law, Kiroro, raped her mother in an open place, after which he drowned her in the River Gidi. The officer also killed her father by chopping him to pieces for vultures to feed on, and then raped Kigeme also not minding that she was still a child. Kigeme becomes pregnant as a result of the rape culminating in her becoming a child-mother. The traumatic war memories at the starting point of the narrative is presented in the third person point of view using flashback narrative technique which abruptly changes to the first-person narrative as Kigeme gives birth to her fruit of rape, Wache Wacheke Watachoka, who now acts as a child narrator in the story. The novel recounts the psychological trauma which Wache goes through when he realizes that he is a product of rape, and not of marital bliss. The story also tells of other traumatic experiences he had as a child-refugee, his challenges as a school pupil at Wirodi, and later as a child-soldier in the bushes, back to Burundi where he was faced with paternal rejection and near dead maltreatment from a man who is his father. He later goes back to Wirodi only to find out that the refugees at Mabanu camp had been forced to return to their country, Burundi. He returns to his home-country as a school pupil, realizing that there is no

family to return to as his father had outrightly rejected him during his last visit to Burundi. On arrival at his motherland at Karibu College in Burundi, he is faced with new traumatic challenges comprising of insults, abuses, humiliations, marginalization and conspiracies from his school mates, teachers and the principal. The major challenge he faces in the college is in terms of the language of instruction, which is French, completely different from the language of instruction at Wirodi which was Kiswahili and English. It is therefore not surprising that he becomes a High School dropout. Wache's fortunes, however, change as he becomes a renowned investor having dropped out from the college and embraced a life of hustling.

In creating her fiction, the author incorporates some facts that are related to traumatic representations. The violence registered in this postcolonial Burundian literature is in line with Michael Rothberg's theory of trauma which submits that trauma "helps make us attentive to suffering and thus, in principle, to justice and responsibility, but it needs to be supplemented by a positive vision of social and political transformation" (Rothberg, 2003:156).

Theoretical framework and methodology:

The study adopts a theoretical framework that will take account of linguistic descriptions, stylistic analyses and literary interpretations since these theories permit in a wide range in the analysis of contemporary style of writing that incorporates facts and fiction. Hence, parameters from style will guide the analysis on choice of a child-refugee as a traumatic voice in Toyi's *Weep Not, Refugee*. One of the descriptions of style by Wales is that of choice from a "general stock of language in any given period" (1989:24). According to Koch, "a particular linguistic is held against what else could have been said or what should have been said" (1963:414), while Hutchings maintains that "stylistics is primarily concerned with accounting for choices among alternative surface structures" (1973:93). Enkvist views style as an "active principle of composition by which the writer penetrates and reveals the inner form of his subject" (1964:10). One other way of looking at style as choice is from the point of view of the reader in which Enkvist explains as "a shell surrounding a pre-existing core of thought or expression... the choice between alternative expressions; a set of individual characteristics" (1964:10- 11). However, these approaches to style as choice can lend one form of insight or the other in the analysis of texts, including even those that derive from impressionistic

traditions. The above explanations on, and approaches to style discuss style from the writer's /speaker's point of view, and from the reader's/listener's perspective.

Toyi's Stylistic Choice:

Toyi's *Weep Not, Refugee* is redolent in linguistic deviations, repetitions, fragmentations, rhetorical strategy, ironies and native proverbial sayings. The novel is written in an orally-inflected, hybridized English and French which combine euro-francophone prose technique with the speech patterns of the author's native language, Kirundi. This highlights adequately issues of split identity and ethnic language politics. Examples of the author's speech pattern seen in the following excerpts from the novel;

"...carrying a leaking **jelly can** of water" (12).

"Your words resemble you!... Is it not you
who gave
pregnancy to Nancy?.." (23)

"... he had followed them to lend them his
hand,..." (87)

In the first example, one clearly sees the mother-tongue influence and errors involving lateral sounds /l/ and /r/ where the narrator ends up using the wrong word '**jelly can**' for 'jerry can'. There is also an obvious transference of the author's native language syntactic structures to the language of narrative.

The omniscient author's point of view in the narratives as seen in the choice and use of the word, 'I' reveals the author as an actively involved spokesperson and this is very prominent in the novel. For example;

"...I am a fruit of rape. I am a result of ethnic
hatred, not love between a man and a woman" (14).

"I grew up with a wound, the wound of being a refugee.

This wound bled as often as crises emerged" (28).

The above declarations make the narrator share and become a part of the ethnic hatred, thereby partaking in the psychological wound, anguish and the eventual trauma occasioned by the wound. Priebe criticizes the idea of exposing the narrator to social violence as he complains that "the author grants far too much understanding to the narrator of the real and historical and

social details of violence" (2005:51). Priebe's submission agrees with Caruth's explanation of trauma that it "has moving and sorrowful voice" (1996:91).

This continuous, though representative use of 'I', makes the narrator to be seen as if in confrontation with an identified enemy. This approach is very prominent in the novel and is frequently made manifest in the speeches of the child narrator. The author establishes the subjectivity of her protagonist through the use of the first-person narrator. Toyi's narrator is Wache Wacheke Watachoka who has very little formal education. On page 21 of the novel, Wache is revealed as a seven year old child-refugee. The frequent employment of the first person narrative through the deployment of the word, "I", heightens the traumatic import of the story. For instance;

"I carry that name without any complaint" (16)

"I saw the camp on fire" (114)

The adverb, 'without', in the first extract, 'I carry that name (Wache) *without* any complaint' is used to show the 'still present' or 'still here' effect of the humiliation tagged to the name. This humiliation is made manifest in the psycho-emotional sphere hence, psychological and mental traumas are revealed. Therefore, anytime the name, Wache, is mentioned, a humiliating feeling of disgrace and embarrassment as to what his mother had to pass through before he was given birth to is evoked. No wonder Tal explains that, "literature of trauma is defined by the identity of its author.... holds at its center the reconstruction and recuperation from the traumatic experience,...." (1996:17). In the second extract, 'I saw the camp on fire', the narrator does not say precisely who is responsible for the ecological unclothing of the refugees. However, the author satirizes man's self-destruction as he destroys his own environment in the quest for vengeance. This act is mentally traumatic to the child-refugee as the sight of the fire razing down some of his brothers in misery and their belongings continues to confront him mentally. It is a sight that chokes and can cause him dementia.

An ideological inclination of the child-narrator is revealed in the under-listed assertions, assertions which portray him as being proud of his identity though a refugee in exile;

"I would prefer to stay with my brothers in misery...."(113)

"My mother would not hear that my head was opened by a rocket.... I had to spare her that agony. She had been living only for me, and I had promised to console her" (73)

The language of expression by the child narrator in the passages above reveals the systematic brotherhood which he confers on his co-victims of pain, deprivations and trauma. The possessive deictic, 'my', is in harmony with the head phrase, 'brothers in misery', to illuminate their plight of discontent, agony and trauma. And 'my brothers in misery' also symbolizes the co-receivers of various actions of humiliations, hate, sufferings, abuses and scorn from both their home-country and the Wirodin nationals. The repetitious use of this same phrase, that is, 'my brothers in misery' and its variants is prominent in the novel. Variants of this phrase and expressions in the novel include "...my brothers in pain..."(27, 49), "...my companions of pain..."(133), and so on and they are all pointers to agony and mystery, the repetitious use of these descriptive adjectives draw attention of people to the plight and predicament of the returnees.

There is what I would like to refer to as the pleasure in trauma in the repetitious use of the nose syndrome in *Weep Not, Refugee*. In this instance, the human nose acquires a national significance and a means of painful ethnic divide. Examples include;

...the time when having a flat nose meant being
an enemy of those with a pointed nose...(48)

"The shape of my nose is different from many
others" (63).

"Your nose is not as pointed as mine..."(97)

"Will a nose buy food for you?... Your flat
nose makes you look uglier"(98)

I remembered the compliments of my friends
in the camp, telling me that I was a handsome
boy, especially because of my pointed nose (98).

...the shape of my nose (99).

It was not an absurd notion of shape of nose
which I had to put in front while searching
for my life partner. (100)

I might have been in the facsimile in the shape
of my nose. Was he not there, in the country,

enjoying life, unworried by the shape of his nose? What about Mr. Kabunda in the camp, a Tutsi who had gone into exile with the Hutus, just because of his flat nose? (100-101).
...in Wirodi, they used to say that we had nose complex....., they said, we were often seen touching our nose for no reason at all (102).

From the illustrations provided above, it can be deduced that part of group trauma is occasioned by a fact of one's physiognomy and not as a result of hurt, harm or hatred. The penultimate illustration above is paradigmatic of this. Mr. Kabunda, a Tutsi has to partake on an exile sojourn with the enemy camp, the Hutus, simply because his physiognomy in terms of nose representation, a flat one at that, is not in tandem with that of his real ethnic group known for their pointed nose. In order to avoid any kind of trauma, he has to proceed on exile with those known for their flat nose.

Generally, the beginning part of *Weep Not, Refugee* reads like a continuous piling up of atrocities committed against, and, hence, injustices suffered by the down-trodden. As an interactive discourse, one can assume that the child-narrator, who is the speaker, is the author herself. She represents the affected jetsam and flotsam of the society, expressing their traumatic experiences by rendering her accounts of acts of brutality and false accusations through the deployment of the narrative technique represented by the word, 'T'. The entire narrative is, hence, the addresser's, (that is the author's) verbal re-echoing of the agonies and trauma inflicted on the child-narrator. Wache, the child-refugee cum narrator, most times, when narrating his traumatic experiences asks rhetorical questions. Instances include;

"only one tiny tent for husband, wife, children, and sometimes one or many relatives, how could someone keep a secret there?" (22)

"who had ever been in exile twice?" (152)

"how many boys had been disowned by their fathers, like me?"(152)

when the narrator makes reference to his encounter with certain absent human actors in the text:

ueless Let me keep quiet, hoping that you guess how
 Mwalimu's threat was. (45)
 ... a pot bellied HCR representative named Mr.
 Yanvrampart introduced. (Excuse me; it is easier
 for me to call him Yamva) (46)

These imperatives, 'let me keep quiet' and 'excuse me', suggest a listener who is present with Wache in a face-to-face encounter and who is transcribing his speech. In other words, it could also be assumed that Wache is directly addressing the reader, given his fictive role within the narrative in a narrator and addressee kind of relationship.

Cultural sentiment is expressed in the novel through the employment of provocative language. This is made evidence in *Weep Not, Refugee* when Wache mischievously addresses, Kigeme, his mother, thus;

not Mummy, do you know the latest? I heard people
 saying that you were a Tutsi, but that they do
 fear you because you are a poor woman. (61)

This is Wache's own way of goading his mother on so she can open up on his true paternity: no one actually leveled the allegation. Wache is only bothered about how to trace his origin. A mental trauma occasioned by helplessness is seen from the above. On the one hand, Wache is traumatized, feeling inadequate for not having a root. On the other, the Tutsi are the majority ethnic group in Burundi and with them lies power. But here is an irony in a toothless bull dog of a Tutsi simply because she is economically incapacitated if not decapitated, thereby lacking in social worth and would not be respected. A worrying issue in the whole saga is that the reader is compelled to wonder why and how Wache, an under-aged and under-educated child-refugee will reason and speak so much like an adult. One is, therefore tempted to believe that the child-refugee's thoughts are patently the author's voice and traumatic identity memories which the fictional narrative re- echoes.

Toyi also establishes cultural sentiment through a story- within-a-story technique in her narrative. This is seen in the dialogue between Mwalimu and the refugees. The refugees' reaction to Mwalimu's threat is likened to the story of the old woman of the 'April Ant joke' told in the text, as witnessed in this extract: "we survived even the heaviest rains of April" (45). The above expression is certainly cultural as it is a response adapted from their folk story. Mwalimu's threat to the refugees could also be viewed as marginalization. The use of the personal pronoun 'we', here, highlights the difference between the human subject who has witnessed certain traumatic events and an interlocutor who is listening to the stories. There is also an evidence of a transition to more complex form of dialogism based on both cultural difference and the ambiguities of linguistic differences. The foreign cum expatriate Principal of Karibu College would not hide his disgust for the wretched Burundian refugee youths who were to report to his college in pursuance of further studies. Curiously, the word, 'Karibu' in Kirundi means 'Welcome' This, in itself, is an irony because, obviously, the college is not a 'welcoming one to the refugees. In the conclusion of the Principal, after subjecting the youths to a lot of dehumanizing situations, thus leading them towards physical and mental trauma, he adds:

The content of the program may not be the same. In fact, a francophone system and an Anglophone system of education cannot be the same. (131-132)

This cultural dilemma through languages of instruction, (French in Burundi and English from Wirodi where they had stayed for many years as refugees) introduces another dimension of marginalization to the refugees even as they return to their home country, Burundi. This contributes to the construction of cultural trauma among the returning refugees. This also is seen in the grammatically and orthographically incorrect French from Wache;

"Bonjour, monsio"(133)

"C'est vwai monsio"(133)

"Monsio le directeur" (146)

The above expressions serve as indicators of Wache's cultural affiliations, while also revealing the narrator's level of education. The author, through this medium, mocks and criticizes policy makers on what should be the language of instruction among Burundians. These policy makers have insisted that

fluent French must be forced on the natives as their *lingua franca* instead of Kirundi or Kiswahili, their national languages. The incorrect orthography of French words also appears as an attempt by the author to establish the authenticity of the narratives as the testimony of a barely literate child-refugee. However, Wache can be described as a polyglot since he uses both English and French languages as well as Kiswahili in his narrative. Toyi's *Weep Not, Refugee*, therefore, serves not only to bridge the gap between a euro-francophone reader but also the gap between Wache and his interlocutors from various social and educational backgrounds who, regardless of their background, may have trouble understanding the individual subject's narrative. The difference therefore between the narrator and his implied addressee becomes experiential in addition to cultural.

Apart from this distinctive prose style using a deliberately ambiguous frame narrative, the author also makes use of the device of repetition to suggest the psychological impact of trauma on her young protagonist. Narrative technique is employed to create a distinctive sort of historical writing in her attempt to reflect on ethnic conflicts and their traumatic import. Repetitions give an insight on how a child may talk while also creating an impression of orality, aside giving more pieces of information on the child refugee's exposure to violence.

Obscenity as marker of trauma

The word, 'obscene' could be considered as that which is repugnant because it bothers on the sensual and erotic in a very offensive and distasteful manner. In Africa, obscenity is seen as a social taboo: it is not only indecent but also disgusting to the senses. More often than not, obscenity tends towards the sexual in a very vulgar and shamelessly arrogant fashion. Obscenity finds a place in Toyi's *Weep Not, Refugee* and it appears as a marker of trauma in the different places where it is used. As a means of communicating the psychological impact of sexual violence, Toyi employs the use of hidden vulgar registers through the child narrator's frequent narrative of the refugee camp's atrocities. Wache's testimony of camp atrocities reflects the obscene nature of his experiences as a child-refugee and of post-colonial government that were responsible for his fate as it provides only one tiny tent for husband, wife and children. This is captured in the novel, thus;

By the time I was seven years old, I had already penetrated the secrets of adults, like many of my

age mates. Take him as a liar that boy who will tell you that, at that age, he had not yet tasted the forbidden fruit. At the age of ten, ... I was given the paternity of the kid, and my ignorance, helped by the guilt of my silly deeds....(21)

In the context of a child-refugee cum narrator, the literary technique of allowing the child narrator to speak with the vocabulary and fluency of an adult is questionable. Wache, in the novel, is presented as an under-educated young child. By a sudden twist of growth, Wache realizes that he is no longer a child in a conventional sense owing to the violence he and his mates have witnessed and perpetrated. The child narrator's language here could as well be analyzed as the author's attempt to represent simply the obscene refugee camp's reality and the child-refugee cum narrator's specific emotional state related to the sexual violence he has experienced and perpetrated. This also draws the reader's attention to the narrator's affective state, thus reflecting how his traumatic experience has affected as reflected in the way he speaks. The author's stylistic choice here is that of a realistic depiction of a potentially traumatized subject narrating his ordeal and experiences, bearing factual witness within the context of the narrative, to what the speaker himself has seen and suffered.

Vituperation as a marker of trauma

Vituperation is an abusive name-calling. This term is identified by Ong as "flyting" which he describes as an "agonistic name-calling" and explains it to be a feature of "oral societies across the world" (1982:45). Wales also acknowledges that it seems "not unrelated to the rapid or stichomythic interchanges of abusive name-calling common in cultures" (1989:179). Vituperation is a key feature in any modern oral discourse on "othering". Othering, as a phenomenon is also painted in Toyi's *Weep Not, Refugee*. The concept of 'othering' privileges a particular culture of group of persons as being superior, more intelligent and better than the 'other' and this often brings about the experience of trauma. In an essay titled "Kalu Uka as a Dramatist: Painting "Othering" and Self- Reclamation of the Niger Delta in *Ikhamma*", Akwang highlights the ingredients of 'othering' to include superiority and a general feeling of being better than the other. He emphasizes the "we" or ""us" group (which is the superior group), in opposition to the "they" or "them"

group, the one considered as the inadequate group. He justifies his arguments with an online explanation source thus:

The practice of "othering" generally leads to a polarization of people into two groups: An "us" group (or "in-group" in jargon), which normally includes the proponent of an idea, and his or her intended audience, and a "them" group (or "out-group") who are the people who are used as an object for hate or mistrust (cited in Johnson and Inegbe, (2013:75) 'Other'. <http://rationalwiki.org/other#mw-head>. Retrieved January 15, 2014

The in-group is noted to sometime employ provocative language in an attempt at self-assertion. The author of *Weep Not, Refugee*, through this linguistic tool, highlights on split identity and ethnic language politics as the returning refugees are caricatured by the principal at Karibu College, in his question: "where did you get this band of comedians from?" (133). The use of the phrase, 'band of comedians', depicts discrimination and marginalization on the Burundian returnees. And it is capable of evoking emotional trauma culminating in an inferiority complex on the part of the returnees. Here, we have a simulation of encounter between two persons, the principal and the returnees. The use of vituperation here is, in fact, closely associated to trauma, hence, it serves as a marker of trauma.

Other typical cases of vituperation as markers of trauma are seen in the following extracts from the text:

"Son of a bitch" (44)

"Do you have any brain at all?"(46)

"Your flat nose makes you look uglier"(98)

"Move ahead, imbecile!" (130)

"Let me feed that lame duck who cannot feed himself!" (157)

A similar case of confrontation, but with a milder tone, is seen in a Wirodin referring to the child-refugee as "refugee Wache" (36). The essence of this

device is to introduce a sense of immediacy to, and enlivens, the otherwise lifeless, voiceless and autotelic text, besides its didactic role.

Mabanu camp as representation of trauma

The textual structure emphasizes the role and significance of Mabanu camp as a symbol of the refugees' agonies. This position seems strengthened by the narrator's own words as follows:

We were at another junction in life. After fleeing for our lives, we had now passed to elements dangerous to our country of origin.

Where did we belong to? Where? Could it be true that we no longer had a country which we could call ours? Was there any other island

on earth, still undiscovered, so that we could go and live there peacefully? (51).

Mabanu camp evokes the picture of physical trauma as sighting the camp alone is a reminder of the many humiliations, stigmatizations and other negative experiences that the refugees are subjected to. The refugees at Mabanu camp in Wirodi represent the violated, the marginalized, and the traumatized class in the narrative. The nature of the sufferings or violations, reflects in the processes as "hunger" (3), "orphanhood" and "widowhood" (4), "raped" and "drowned"(5), "child labour" and "child traffickers"(75), "injured" (75), and so on.

Child-refugee cum narrator of history

Much of what Wache, the child-refugee cum narrator narrates in the novel describes historical events for which he was not present as the young protagonist claims in his narration in the text;

"after all, I had only heard of war, but I had not yet seen any. Yes, I had almost fought as a child soldier, but Kigeme had always told me that I had not seen anything like war" (92).

Wache has been reduced to a mouthpiece for the author's indictment of Burundian leaders and warlords who are responsible for the violence in the

land. The precision with which the child narrator narrates the history of certain regions, for instance, appears to contradict the assertion in the novel that he is under-educated, a move which arguably detracts from Toyi's framing of the novel as narrated by a child- refugee. A typical example is drawn from the novel, thus:

... I was going to cross to Burundi. I had multiplied the advice of my mother with zero.... With her advice left in the dustbin, I boarded a vehicle for the perilous journey to my home country. When I reached a region where people spoke my mother's language, I started greeting some of them cheerfully, admiring everything and everybody, trying to guess how beautiful my mother's village might be (92-93).

From the citation above, one wonders if the author does not hide behind the voice of this child-refugee who was born at Mabanu camp in wirodi to tell the story. Another example of this strategy occurs in the beginning part of the novel when the child-refugee begins to describe traumatic events for which he was not present;

When she gave birth to me, her pain was no longer written on her face. I am not saying that all her pain had gone. It had penetrated deep into her heart, carving there a deep wound which I inherited at my birth. Just think of it: I am a fruit of rape. I am a result of ethnic hatred, not of love between man and a woman. My father is the murderer of my mother's parents, the cause of her orphanhood and her miserable life, the cause of my misery as well (14)

From the extract above, one may ask: what are the affective implications of narrating a trauma provoking event in the voice of a child as a witness to history? However, given the distance between the life experience of the child narrator and the content of the novel, it is crucial to note the historical dimension of Toyi's writing, and the way in which she uses the device of the child-narrator to provide accounts of some pathetic and traumatic atrocities.

Toyî's narrative is not strictly an historical writing: her narration of quotidian and real life events that have little bearing on the Child-refugee's story functions as witnessing historical events. To LaCapra, this technique can be seen as;

An aspect of understanding which stylistically upsets the narrative voice and counteracts harmonizing narration or unqualified objectification yet allows for a tense interplay between critical, necessarily objectifying reconstruction and affective response to the voices of victims (2001:60).

Therefore, describing and narrating the events through a child's voice can be viewed as an attempt to create an affective response to the voice of a victim while avoiding the 'objectifying reconstruction' that would not elicit a sufficient critical response on the part of the reader.

The most striking example of Toyi's engagement with history through the voice of her child narrator is the account of violence and dismemberment of some of his mates. The reader is struck not simply by the disturbing facts, but by the tone of the child narrator:

I spent less than a week in the maquis: the fire I saw there was something else. The enemies were using heavy artillery, while we had only Kalashnikovs for our defense. I saw a bullet tearing the leg of my friend, Cetina. I saw Bernard volatilized by a rocket. Then I saw Dedano shattered in a bomb blast,... (sic) (72)

Reading through this narration, one reasons and then wonders if the child narrator is not too young to understand the full horror of what he has described or is he already hardened to it? The reader's affective response and understanding of the historical event is thus shaped by the presence of the child narrator's voice, a move which avoids an objectifying account of the event itself. The author has conditioned the voice of the child narrator for historical purposes, adding new complexity to the reader's understanding of events which he may have encountered before, through a stylistic choice preconceived to create this reaction of traumatic language.

Conclusion

Marie-Thérèse Toyi's use of a child's voice as a stylistic choice for her narrative helps to deconstruct the symbolic identity of the child refugee, creating a space for reflection in the way in which the figure of his identity

obscures the subjectivity of the individual human actors upon whom it is based. The analysis shows that personal pronouns play not only the traditional deictic role of 'pointing' or 'indicating', but are also involved in the patterning of the ideological divides and dialectics of the text. The analysis, even in the lexical and semantic levels, has so far tended to confirm the narrator's voice to be highly traumatized in the choice of language codes and styles of narrative.

Repetitions within the text serve as markers of trauma which Toyi's narrator attempts to communicate with his implied addressee. The author's decision to draw the reader's attention towards her protagonist's suffering can be translated as an effort to prevent overly historicized interpretation that would foreclose a more nuanced reflection on the broader psychological impact of the trauma suffered by child refugees.

The focus on violence and traumatic representation in the novel is not solely to give an account or tales of ethnic conflicts and civil war in Burundi, but a clarion which calls the readers to critically reflect on the traumatic happenings in their regions and then proffer an ethno-cultural and political understanding of the situation so as to curb violence and make the society a peaceful place to habit.

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